

The Benefits of a Silvoarable Agroforestry System and the Supports Available in Ireland

www.af4eu.eu

Silvoarable agroforestry system (Photo: Teagasc)
Varied vegetable crop with *Salix* spp. shelterbelt

In Ireland's temperate climate, natural succession shapes ecosystems, improving soil depth, organic matter, and biodiversity. Traditional horticulture focuses on annual crops, thriving in early succession after grazing or tilling. Soil health shifts from bacteria-dominant in early stages to fungi-rich in mature ecosystems, improving nutrient cycling and plant growth. Integrating trees and shrubs like hazel (*Corylus avellana* L.) and blackthorn (*Prunus spinosa* L.) into horticulture enhances soil health, biodiversity, and productivity.

Establishing a silvoarable agroforestry system requires assessing soil, climate, and topography. A well-planned design balances food production, timber, and ecosystem services like wind shelter, erosion control, and biodiversity. While trees compete for local resources, proper tree management through pruning, coppicing, and pollarding minimizes competition. Espalier training optimizes space for fruit trees, while coppicing species like willow (*Salix* spp.) and alder (*Alnus glutinosa* L.) improve soil fertility and provide materials.

Deep-rooted trees reduce competition and improve resource use. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) uses tree layers and understory plants to attract natural predators, reducing chemical inputs to the crop. Native trees, such as oak (*Quercus robur* L.) and hazel, support biodiversity by providing habitats for pollinators and wildlife. Shade-tolerant crops like blackcurrants (*Ribes nigrum* L.), chokeberry (*Aronia* spp.), rhubarb (*Rheum rhabarbarum* L.), and herbs diversify income and improve resilience.

Ireland's Forest Type 8 – Agroforestry scheme promotes tree planting alongside food production. Eligible land must be at least 0.5 hectares, with a minimum of 400 trees per hectare. Landowners can receive €6,000 per hectare (excluding fencing) and an annual payment of €829 per hectare for 10 years, available to both farmers and non-farmers. By integrating trees and crops, Irish farmers can enhance soil health, boost biodiversity, and improve long-term sustainability.

References

Westaway, S., Kling, C., & Smith, J. (2018). A comparison of the performance of three sward mixtures sown under trees in a silvopoultry system in the UK. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(4), 1009–1018.

Smith, J., & Wells, A. (2001). Silvo-Poultry: An Agroforestry System for Organic Chicken Production at Sheepdrove Organic Farm. *The Organic Research Centre*.

John Casey

Teagasc- the Agriculture
and Food Development Authority, Ireland

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.